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Integration of Courses and Projects - disrupting a traditional PBL semester structure

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ABSTRACT

Universities are showing a new and stronger focus on developing teaching and learning environments, using digitalized support as well as re-organizing teaching and learning structures. Connected to the research project *Future directions for PBL in a Digital Age*, we are focusing on the organization of courses and projects within one semester. The general semester structure at Aalborg University consists of three parallel courses and one project module. A consequence of that model has been that interaction between study activities has become less coordinated, and integration between courses and projects has diminished. This lack of integration is a key focus of this paper, and the main research questions are; do students and teachers find that courses and projects need to be more integrated? What are students' experiences regarding integration of courses and project work, and how do they see the benefits and concerns? To answer the questions, we have conducted a survey among students at a case semester. The survey opened up for integrating students' experiences in developing new teaching and learning strategies.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The problem-based learning (PBL) model at Aalborg University is known for a strong emphasis on learning through students' own projects, supporting a mix of collaboration skills as well as subject specific skills, through an integrated structure of course work and project work [1], [2], [3]. The PBL approach is based on 9 guiding principles which are reflected in teaching, supervision/facilitation and project work [4]. Although the AAU PBL-model is a distinctive feature of AAU, the principles have been challenged in recent years, where lack of resources has meant that it has been difficult to unfold curricula accordingly, and to introduce the basic PBL principles in students' learning processes [5]. A new research project, *Future Directions for PBL in a Digital Age* is carried out from 2017-20 at Aalborg University (AAU) Denmark, with an overall aim to review and challenge the AAU PBL model [6]. One of the research questions is connected to integration of courses and students' projects. Traditionally, a semester is equally divided between courses and project work – both running in parallel during a semester. However, a current tendency is that many courses require extra time, thus taking necessary time away from students' semester projects [7]. We consequently consider it an important challenge to reestablish a better interplay between courses and students' project work. This paper will focus on students' experiences, benefits and concerns, regarding integration of courses and project work. The study will deal with the 4th semester at Medialogy at the AAU Copenhagen campus, and will primarily be based on experiences from 5th semester students (the previous 4th semester).

2 COURSES AND PROJECTS

The AAU principles related to problem-based and project-organized work implies a structure for the educational programs at the university where half of the semester is used on courses and half of the semester is used on student-led project work (semester projects). While there are specific differences regarding the structure between different programs, the courses are meant to support the semester projects, in which a high emphasis is placed on students working problem-based and project-organized. The AAU learning strategies and pedagogical ideas of active, social and student-centred learning, has to be integrated in both course-work and project-work, but with a tendency where course activities take too much time away from the semester project work, the balance in the AAU model is influenced. It is important to sustain the PBL project-work, but also to keep improving the possibilities for students to use their courses in new ways. One example is to keep improving students' ability to apply and test theories and methods learned in courses, in their semester projects [4]. This is a unique possibility for students' learning processes, and central to AAU's PBL model. However, we conducted a small pilot survey (June 2018), where 19 students from Medialogy 4th semester were interviewed about several aspects from one course (Audio Processing). To the question, if the students had used elements from the course in their semester projects, 17 of the 19 students answered "no" or "not really". Qualitative responses showed students' reasons for not using course elements in the project, stating that they were not considered relevant (or very far from the project). A few students added "*we could have used it, we just didn't*" [7]. While the limited sample size is not representative for the university programs, it suggests a very concrete problem within its PBL model, where students do not automatically integrate knowledge from the courses into their project work. Possible explanations could be that it is too difficult to integrate courses and projects because of lack of time for

implementation, or that the structure of a semester does not inherently support the interplay among courses and projects, but rather the individual isolation of each.

When looking at a semester design like 4th semester at the Bachelor program of Medialogy 2018 (figure 1), we see how courses, activities related to courses, and exams are spread out during the semester. The study intensity for such semester is 30 ECTS, which is converted to approximately 825 hours of work (1 ECTS = 27.5 hour). For the 4th semester at Medialogy, it means that the study intensity for 3 courses of 5 ECTS each, sums to 412,5 hours of expected work. The exact same workload is prescribed for the semester-project, per student. Students are expected to work on their semester project in parallel with the courses [8]. The way students are using their study-time is based on their individual choice. However, there are some study-activities, which are fixed, both content- and calendar-wise, between exams, course assignments, mini projects and semester project work deadlines. There also are some expectations. Course teachers e.g. expect that students do prepare (homework) according to the course plans, and participate in course exercises. Students need to organize their study time according to the semester plan, as illustrated in figure 1, and coordinate the different activities connected to courses and semester group work. This often is a challenge, as the difficulty levels of the activities may be experienced differently between students and teachers. The way students experience a semester is very important for our main questions: 1) How can the courses be integrated in the semester projects, and how can the semester projects integrate the course elements and at the same time improve students' learning process? 2) How do students see possibilities of integrating courses and projects?

Figure 1: Semester plan activities at 4th semester Media-technology (Medialogy) at Aalborg University [9]

3 METHODS

3.1 Data collection

We have used an explorative case study approach [10], [11], [12] to investigate the context and content of a 4th semester, as background to investigate students' experiences about their Medialogy 4th semester. Included in this context were the study regulation, and students' grades in courses and projects. The parameters of these aspects were reflected in the survey questions, that had space for qualitative explanations to supplement the quantitative answers. The study explored the students'

experiences about courses and semester projects, within the semester curriculum and structure. The following parts were addressed:

- Relation between course curricula and projects
- Workload related to courses and projects
- Students reflections on the 4th semester

In order to acquire data about students' experiences of their 4th semester we distributed a questionnaire to all 5th semester students (previous 4th semester) in autumn 2018. The data were analyzed according to the importance of the following questions:

1. Did project work support understanding of courses, and how easy were the courses to transfer to projects? Those questions were followed by the respondents' qualitative explanations of the answers.
2. Did course teachers make it easy to understand how the courses could be integrated in the projects? This question were followed by qualitative comments and explanations of the answers by the respondents.
3. Workload related to the 3 courses, the projects and exams.

Finally, students were asked to comment specifically on the questions of why there were generally given higher grades for project exams than for course exams, and they were encouraged to reflect generally on their 4th semester. We distributed a questionnaire divided in 3 parts: relationship between course curricula and project; students' workload in courses and project; and closing reflections. The parts included 10 quantitative items asking for ratings, and 4 qualitative items, asking for elaborating comments on specific rating types, or for reflections on certain topics. The qualitative additions were rich and added important insights.

4. RESULTS

In the following, the results from the questionnaire are presented. The quantitative items asked students to rate their answers on a 7-point scale (e.g. 6 being very high and 0 being none or very low). 38 students (out of 61 on the semester) completed the entire questionnaire, whereas 6 students completed all but the final part 3 (closing reflections). As part 3 is all qualitative, we had n=44 respondents to all quantitative items. For an overview of all 10 quantitative items, see **table 1** in the appendix.

Part 1 are analysed within the frame of the main question on students' experiences about integration of courses and project work. The name of the three courses are: Audio Processing (AP), Design and Analysis of Experiments (DAE) and Physical Interface Design (PID).

4.1. PART 1: Relationship between course curricula and project

Q1: How important were the individual courses for your project?

- AP course: rated 6 by 24%, 5 by 13% and 2 to 0 by 34%.
- DAE course: rated 6 of 37%, 5 by 26% and 2 to 0 by 8%.
- PID course: rated 6 by 39%, 5 by 16% and 2 to 0 by 30%.

Q2: How important was your project to support your understanding of the individual courses' content?

- AP course: rated 6 by 13%, 5 by 5% and 2 to 0 by 35%.
- DAE course: rated 6 by 37%, 5 by 37% and 2 to 0 by 6%.
- PID course: rated 6 by 18%, 5 by 13% and 2 to 0 by 37%.

Q3: How easy was the course content (lectures, homework, practical exercises) to transfer/use in your project?

- AP course: rated 6 by 5%, 5 by 13% and 2 to 0 by 32%.
- DAE course: rated 6 by 39%, 5 by 29% and 2 to 0 by 6%.
- PID course: rated 6 by 16%, 5 by 26% and 2 to 0 by 29%.

Across the Q1, Q2 and Q3, the DAE course differentiates itself among the courses, being consistently rated highly by most students, as important for the project, supported by the project, and easily transferrable to the project. The PID course is less consistent on the importance of the course for the project, being rated both high and low by many students, but, interestingly scoring consistently low ratings by many students, in terms of its support for course understanding, and transfer of the course to the project. The AP course followed the trend of PID, albeit much lower ratings.

Q4: Qualitative student reflections for low Q1, Q2, Q3 ratings:

All students rating 3 or lower, were asked to comment on their specific rating. The comments cover several aspects. Some of the main problems seem to confirm previous tendencies; that courses were not relevant for the projects: *"We did not apply the theory learned in the course at all because it was not relevant"*. Another issue was that the difficulty level in courses was perceived to be too high, making course topics too difficult to fully comprehend, compared to the perceived benefits to the project. There also seems to be a negative loop, where course material is disregarded per default, if not understood to be supportive of the project: *"The courses were hard to transfer as it covers so much and can be hard to follow", "It was too difficult, and we did not have much use for it in the semester project, as we did not put much focus on it"*. Finally, some students mentioned that the timing of the course did not fit with the project process: *"The DAE course had some lectures very late in the semester which was very essential to the progress of making the project...we wish we had some of the later lectures, earlier, which would help us form the report in a different way"*. Interesting is that some students seems to combine courses with a lot of self-studies: *"We did not actually use any of the course material (except maybe a general understanding) and generally haven't in a single of the semesters. We go out of our way to find the suitable tests and research them on our own, and our problems, solutions, implementations etc. are never close to anything presented in class"*.

Q5: To which degree did the course teachers make it easy for you to understand how their courses could be integrated into the project?

- AP course: rated 6 by 5%, 5 by 8% and 2 to 0 by 43%.
- DAE course: rated 6 by 51%, 5 by 24% and 2 to 0 by 5%.
- PID course: rated 6 by 11%, 5 by 16% and 2 to 0 by 5%.

Here, DAE is very highly rated by students (with over half awarding 6), PID shows neither very high or low ratings, while AP receives many 0-2 ratings as the only course.

Q6: Qualitative student reflections for high Q5 ratings:

All students rating 4 or higher were asked to comment on why they had this impression, for insights to how teachers succeeded to integrate courses into projects. Comment themes included: using lots of examples in courses; practical exercises; a clear structure in the courses; and the direct applicability in projects. *"Course teachers can use projects as examples to explain how to understand and implement course knowledge in projects", "We were given examples that incorporated both courses in a project", "The whole theory of statistics was nicely presented and the math, although complicated, was thoroughly worked with in both practical exercises and with many wonderful videos that supplemented my learning. This is the best course I had so far on the entire education", "The teachers made it super easy with their ways of explaining the courses and helping us to relay them into the course project", "DAE specifically was constantly emphasized to be relevant for the semester project, with lots of examples, practical exercises and a clear structure".*

Q7: To which degree did your supervisor encourage you to connect course content from the individual courses, to the project?

- AP course: rated 6 by 24%, 5 by 19% and 2 to 0 by 19%.
- DAE course: rated 6 by 22%, 5 by 11% and 2 to 0 by 24%.
- PID course: rated 6 by 16%, 5 by 19% and 2 to 0 by 37%.

For all courses, some students felt encouraged to connect course content to the semester projects. However, a group of students did not experience this across the courses, which isn't reflecting the intended supervision experience of the AAU model.

4.2. PART 2: Workload between courses and project

Q8: How would you rate the workload for homework and self-studies for each individual course?

- AP course: rated 6 by 3%, 5 by 19% and 2 to 0 by 24%.
- DAE course: rated 6 by 5%, 5 by 22% and 2 to 0 by 13%.
- PID course: rated 6 by 8%, 5 by 5% and 2 to 0 by 52%

Q9: How would you rate the workload for course exams incl. preparation?

- AP course: rated 6 by 46%, 5 by 32% and 2 to 0 by 3%
- DAE course: rated 6 by 46%, 5 by 20% and 2 to 0 by 8%.
- PID course: rated 6 by 30%, 5 by 30% and 2 to 0 by 14%

Between Q8 and Q9, a clear discrepancy shows between students' highest effort, with only few students working hard on the course curriculum during the semester, and a much higher number putting high effort post-project, to comprehend the courses.

Q10: How would you rate the workload for project related group work?

- Rated 6 by 46%, 5 by 24%, and 2 to 0 by 3%.

More than half the 4th semester students report a maximum or high effort during groupwork-based project work, with nearly none reporting low effort.

Q11: How would you rate the workload connected to individual self-study, individually, in group room, home or other places?

- Rated 6 by 16%, 5 by 19%, and from 2 to 0 by 19%.

For individual work on project related things, fewer students give high ratings, and more give low ratings, compared to in-situ shared group-work.

Q12: “Workload connected to project exam, including preparation”?

- Rated 6 by 32%, 5 by 30%, and 2 to 0 by 14%.

Many students report high effort in the (often group-collaborative) project exam preparations. The scores reflect the course exams, but different from courses, they also reflect the effort found in group-work activities.

4.3. PART 3: Closing reflections from the students

Q13: Student reflections on the relationship and difference in grades between projects and courses

While most students rated the workload of the course- and the project exams very similarly, students were asked into their opinion on the relationship and differences between these, based on a background dataset, showing that students' projects received much higher grades than their course exams. The reflections students did for this question circled on three aspects:

- The difference between courses and projects, and their individual exams.
- The perception of grading, between courses and projects.
- The different ways of learning via courses and projects.

Many students mentioned that teachers' expectations towards students' learning ability, had great importance: *“The courses take up too much time and carry too high expectations, for the time allotted, while most effort seems aimed towards the project”*.

A similarly striking statement came in the form of *“We were able to get a very good grade for our project by using very little course material. But very low grades for the courses. There are bigger expectations for the course exams”*, suggesting that the experienced level required for a high project grade is lower than the courses. In addition, another tendency showed that some students believe that using course material in the projects, mean nothing for the project grading: *“Project work seems more motivating for the students and it seems easier to get good grades”*. Some also consider projects as more important from a career perspective, and are therefore considered more attractive to excel, compared to courses: *“It seems that people want to focus on the projects as it is something one could add to their portfolio and making a good project only makes it better. This takes some of the focus away from the courses to an extent where they become guiding aspects for the project rather than important knowledge for Medialogy students”*. As seen in the previous ratings, the collaborative, interdependent and supporting aspect of project work is considered a big motivation factor: *“the motivation of group work is big factor, where students can rely and ask each other. The actual courses are solely dependent on the individual”*. The aspects above are logically reflected in the following statement on coursework:

“Courses require significantly more of the individual, not only in the workload but in the individual dedication to the courses”.

Q14: Students' recommendations on how courses can support projects - or how projects can support courses

The students' recommendations are very practically oriented and even quite feasible. Some suggest project-based courses, courses based on mini-projects, or for courses to include the projects more in course assignments: *“More project-based courses, so you are making smaller projects that use the course material, making it more motivating. Learning by really doing”.* *“Courses should include the projects more in assignments (both mandatory and obligatory), that way student might see the threads connecting the courses and project more clearly. Of course this might be difficult to implement, as people have very different projects but I really think it could have helped our projects throughout the education”.* *“Project work is great, maybe force the projects to have more core concepts from the courses”.* *“The semester project theme suggestions are nice to show some potential ideas or to give direction. The teachers and supervisors should be on the same page if and to what extent the course content should be included in the semester project”.* *“More emphasis on course inclusion - eventually a supervisor reminding us of the fact that they all more or less need to be included”.* The recommendations are dealing with aspects of integrating courses and projects, where project work is seen to be able to bring passion and motivation into *both* courses and project-work. Some recommendations also mention the role of the supervisor/facilitator, as a supporting agent of integration for course and project. And the importance for teachers and supervisors to align 'on the same page'.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

When looking at the results, they confirm previous tendencies; that courses are perceived to be less relevant to projects. Remembering how the AAU PBL model frames courses as the foundation of the project content and academic workload, it is alarming that so many students rate the courses' relevance for the project this low.

In the qualitative responses, we see that students have many reasons for not prioritizing the integration of courses and projects. Workload ratings for courses suggest that courses are not deemed necessary for the projects, as otherwise, they would not need to study as hard for the exams. Arguments include not believing integration or transfer to be necessary, and not perceiving the urgency from the teaching staff (including supervisors). Some students even state that they do not believe that the project needs any course content. To learn 'useful skills' directs Medialogy students' effort and motivation to learn. From our results, students perceive projects as useful learning, for developing their individual portfolios. This partly cements the projects' priority amongst many students, and also arguably illustrates why the courses do not receive similar priority. The transfer of knowledge happens when found useful by students. In this case, transfer means integration between courses and project, ideally with transfer of knowledge between both. However, students generally, ironically, do not see that relationship or potential. While this could be considered a serious issue from a Medialogy-program centric point of view, the case could also be less so, and more an issue of succeeding with the facilitation and management of the course-project integration. Such effort is important for upholding

and developing the AAU Model, and to support quality of what students clearly enjoy, and are motivated by the most.

Upholding the AAU model on a semester is no trivial task. It is partly an issue from a semester coordination and management perspective, to define and set clear curricula goals from the semester's overall learning goals, and make them fit holistically with each other. In our results, we get several recommendations from students to improve such integration. They request examples, exercises, structure and direct application in projects. While these are logical guidelines to integrate courses into projects, it also requires the project scope to be manageable from a course planning perspective. If students are free to take their project in a wide range of directions, no course will ever be able to show relevant examples, hit relevant exercises, or provide knowledge that directly applies to projects. In this case, it seems that a possible barrier for the possibility of integration, has been not limiting the specific project framing sufficiently in scope. Students' recommendations also suggest, that if the project direction is managed sufficiently, forming a connection for integration should not be exceedingly complicated; from examples of project application, to the activation of students in-class through practical exercises for more cultivation and familiarization with course material. All should benefit students' transfer of knowledge and integration between courses and projects. Students also mention the importance of courses' timing through the project phases, and having a clear structure of the course. For integration, *timing* the project and course refers to a 'transfer window' so to speak, where students are able to both comprehend material and see its application (or integration) potential. If arriving too late in a course, students will have missed the chance, or been forced to move on from the possibility of implementing it into the project. Meanwhile, extending this 'transfer window' may be achieved through, exactly, a clear and transparent *course structure*, that ideally maps itself to the faculty's overall directions and expectations for the project's progression curve. Students should obviously not be expected to fully comprehend such mapping prematurely. It could be introduced at semester start, and be referenced regularly in all courses, to grow with students along the semester. Students could use the overview to foresee possible 'transfer windows' for integration of course material in the project.

Another central theme in the results, is the high workload effort in all group-based activities. When students meet and collaborate, e.g. in projects, qualitative responses suggest a shared experience of mutual stake and accountability. This could indicate that it's not so much about the project, but about the collaboration. The lower ratings on performing project work individually, would support this to a certain degree. In this sense, projects are largely different from the highly individual-oriented courses, where the individual student's workload has to be undertaken outside collaboration. And while exam workloads are similar between courses and project, students' ratings show a very different effort during the process leading to the respective exams. In our results, students report that courses tend to require more from the individual dedication to the courses, and that courses require a higher level to pass, compared to the projects. Within these statements lies a potential consideration for rebalancing the (perceived) coursework requirements opposite students' impressions of project work requirements, but the premise is highly relative and unclear. Project work could easily be equally demanding, but dismissed as so, being driven by motivational factors such as autonomy and group collaboration factors previously mentioned. This supports the need for well-implemented course-project integration, bringing the course content and workflow closer to the project work.

Meanwhile, our study has shown that there are students who find the courses relevant in relation to their project work, and who also find that teachers have been keen to find examples and cases which students could relate to. Each course is different and students have rated them differently. Where some students find them too hard to understand, it may be due to a lack of the required knowledge from previous semesters, or because students focus on their most difficult course in a comment, forgetting about the other courses. The workload related to the daily course activities was graded to be less than the workload when preparing for both course- and project exams that was graded to be very high. This could be because the semester structure/activities did challenge both students as well as teachers' ability to manage time and activities connected to both courses and projects. It is also important to mention that while our results look at the specific 4th Medialogy semester, it is very likely that students' attitudes do not only stem from the 4th semester, but also from previous semesters. This points towards upholding the AAU model consistently through all semesters. Developing a culture where students are confident in the relevant role of both courses and project is imperative. Sustaining it is just as imperative. Consistency is necessary across all semesters for a model such as AAU's to work. If not kept throughout, students will adapt to the premise they see in front of them, according to their own interests and gains, as it shows from our results. This study has shown that there are several possibilities to integrate courses and projects in a teaching and learning strategy. The students had good reflections and recommendations. Other possibilities include a semester model using more digitized support in a blended learning strategy, perhaps via student-teacher co-creation workshop, for designing a new semester as a democratic process, with both students and teachers as experts.

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References

- [1] deGraff, E. and Kolmos, A. (2003), Characteristics of Problem-Based Learning. *International Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 19, No. 5, pp. 657-662.
- [2] Aalborg University (2015), PBL – Problem-based learning. http://www.aau.dk/digitalAssets/148/148025_pblaalborg-model_uk.pdf
- [3] Holgaard, J.E., Dahms, M., and Kolmos, A. (2017), Empowering students to co-construct the PBL environment. *International Research Symposium on PBL: PBL, Social Progress and Sustainability*. Aalborg University Press, pp. 386-398.
- [4] Askehave, I., Linnemann Prehn, H., Pedersen, J., and Thorsø Pedersen, M. (red.)(n.d.), PBL: Problem Baseret Læring. Aalborg universitet. Rektorsekretariatet. Retrieved from http://www.aau.dk/digitalAssets/148/148026_pbl

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- [5] Davidsen, J. and Konnerup, U. (2016), Revitalisering af PBL i videregående uddannelser gennem Learning Design. *Læring og Medier (LOM)*, Vol. 9, No. 15.
- [6] Future directions of PBL in a digital age (2018). Retrieved from <http://www.pblfuture.aau.dk>
- [7] Kofoed, L.B., Kristensen, N.S., Andreasen, L.B., Bruun-Pedersen, J.R. and Høeg, E.R. (2018), Integrating Courses and Project Work to Support PBL: a conceptual design for changing curriculum structure. In Wang, Kolmos, Guerra, and Qiao (Eds.), *7th International Research Symposium on PBL: Innovation, PBL and Competences in Engineering Education*. Aalborg University Press, Aalborg, Danmark, pp. 260-268.
- [8] Curriculum for the Bachelor Program in Medialogy (2017). Retrieved from https://www.sict.aau.dk/digitalAssets/283/283409_bsc-medialogy.pdf
- [9] Hüttel, H. and Gnaur, D. (2017), If PBL is the answer, then what is the problem? *Journal of Problem Based Learning in Higher Education*, Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 1-21.
- [10] Remenyi, D. (2013), Case study research, *Academic Conferences and Publishing International*, Reading, UK.
- [11] Yin, V.K. (2008), Case study research: Design and methods, Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- [12] Savin Baden, M. and Toms, G. (2018), Research Methods For Education In The Digital Age. Bloomsbury Academic, London.

Appendix 1, Table 1 - Quantitative results overview

V	Question	Course	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
Q1	How important were the courses for your project?	Audio Processing (AP)	24%	13%	26%	3%	13%	18%	3%
		Design and Analysis of Experiments (DAE)	37%	26%	21%	8%	3%	5%	0%
Q2	How important was your project to support your understanding of your course content?	Physical Interface Design	39%	16%	13%	3%	3%	11%	16%
		Audio Processing (AP)	13%	5%	13%	13%	21%	26%	8%
Q3	How easy was the course content (lectures, home-work, practical exercises to transfer to your project?	Design and Analysis of Experiments (DAE)	37%	37%	13%	8%	3%	0%	3%
		Physical Interface Design (PID)	18%	13%	18%	13%	8%	8%	21%
Q4	To which de-ree did the course teachers make it easy for you to understand to integrate courses?	Audio Processing (AP)	5%	13%	47%	3%	11%	16%	5%
		Design and Analysis of Experiments (DAE)	39%	29%	24%	3%	3%	0%	3%
Q5	To which degree did your supervisor encourage you to connect course content to your semester project?	Physical Interface Design (PID)	16%	26%	29%	0%	11%	5%	13%
		Audio Processing (AP)	5%	8%	19%	24%	27%	11%	5%
Q6	Workload: Homework and selfstudes related to courses?	Design and Analysis of Experiments (DAE)	51%	24%	8%	11%	5%	0%	0%
		Physical Interface Design (PID)	11%	16%	24%	30%	8%	5%	5%
Q7	Workload: Exam incl. preparation	Audio Processing (AP)	24%	19%	24%	14%	16%	3%	0%
		Design and Analysis of Experiments (DAE)	22%	11%	30%	14%	5%	14%	5%
Q8	Workload: Project group work	Physical Interface Design (PID)	16%	19%	11%	16%	5%	11%	22%
		Audio Processing (AP)	3%	19%	35%	19%	16%	5%	3%
Q9	Workload: Self-study for project	Design and An-lysis of Expe-ri-ments (DAE)	5%	22%	32%	27%	5%	8%	0%
		Physical Interface Design (PID)	8%	5%	11%	24%	11%	27%	14%
Q10	Workload: project exam	Audio Processing (AP)	46%	32%	14%	5%	0%	0%	3%
		Design and An-lysis of Expe-ri-ments (DAE)	46%	20%	24%	3%	8%	0%	0%
Q10	Workload: project exam	Physical Interface Design (PID)	30%	30%	11%	16%	14%	0%	0%
		Meetings, communication, collaborative activities	46%	24%	24%	3%	3%	0%	0%
Q9	Workload: Self-study for project	Studying individually in group rooms, home or any other place	16%	19%	35%	11%	16%	3%	0%
		Including preparation	32%	30%	16%	8%	11%	3%	0%